

Institut-Hôpital
neurologique de Montréal

Montreal Neurological
Institute-Hospital

EDDU Protocols

Generation of OPCs and Oligodendrocytes from iPSCs

Authors: Piscopo, Valerio and Durcan, Thomas M.

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The involved functions approve the document for its intended use:

Name	Function	Role	Date	Signature
Dr. Thomas Durcan	R&D	Associate Director, MNI Early Drug Discovery Unit (EDDU)		

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1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives

This protocol describes how to:

- Generate and culture oligodendrocyte progenitor cells (OPCs) from iPSCs
- Differentiate and culture functional myelinating oligodendrocytes

1.2 Protocol overview

By using a combination of small molecules and growth factors that regulate multiple pathways we adapted a method to induce and pattern spinal cord-like neural progenitor cells (sc-NPCs), to differentiate them into OPCs and to expand them within 75 days. OPCs can be expanded and stored or differentiated into fully functional myelinating oligodendrocytes within 20 days.

Figure 1, Schematics of the differentiation protocol

1.3 Technical and safety considerations

The following information should be read before starting:

- sc-NPCs, OPCs and oligodendrocytes must be handled within a Class II biosafety laminar flow hood to protect the worker from possible adventitious agents. Environmental Health and Safety (EHS) office regulations must be followed.
- The quality of materials used in this protocol is critical to its success. Refer to the Materials section for recommended suppliers and catalogue numbers.
- NPCs and OPCs may be recovered from a frozen stock or generated from iPSCs.
- All media should be prepared fresh and only in the amount needed for that day. Excess media may be stored at 4°C for up to 10 days but it is preferable to use freshly prepared media. As a general rule, it is possible to create a basal medium to be stored for a maximum of 10 days into which appropriate molecules and growth factors can be added fresh when needed.
- OPCs and oligodendrocytes must be cultured on surfaces coated with poly-L-ornithine (PO) and laminin (except during the suspension phase to enrich for Olig-2 positive pre-OPCs)

- **Take extra precautions to maintain sterility:**
 - Aspirate media using a 200 µl tip placed on top of a 1-mL plastic serological pipet and change to a new tip frequently.
- **Manipulate cells gently:**
 - Add and aspirate media to vessels slowly and resuspend cells slowly. If possible, avoid adding media directly onto cells (e.g. dispense media onto the upper interior surface of the flask or onto the side of well of the plate).
 - Mix cells in a tube by pipetting slowly a few times or by gently inverting. Do not over-pipette cells.
 - Avoid shaking plates when handling them; OPCs and oligodendrocytes tend to form layers that are loosely attached and can easily detach from the plate.
- **Maintain a stable culture environment for cells during incubation:**
 - Culture vessels should be placed toward the back of the cell culture incubator shelf to maintain stable temperature and CO₂ levels when the door of the incubator is opened and closed.
 - When dissociating cells, use a different 37°C incubator than cell culture incubator to minimize opening and closing the door of the cell culture incubator. **Note** that the dissociation incubator should be sterile but does not require a CO₂ supply.
- OPC cultures must be monitored regularly to ensure optimal morphology and density prior to differentiation.

2 Materials

Refer to the product datasheet from the supplier for further details on storage and preparation instructions.

2.1 Labware

Item	Supplier	Catalogue #
Conical tube, 15-mL	Thermo Fisher	352097
Cryovial	Sarstedt	72.379
Culture flask, T25	Thermo Fisher	12-556-009
Culture flask, T75	Thermo Fisher	12-556-010
Culture plate, 6-well	Thermo Fisher	087721B
Culture plate, 96-well Black/Clear Flat Bottom	Falcon	353219
Petri-dish, 100-mm	Thermo Fisher	FB0875712
12 Well Chamber, removable	Ibidi	81201
Plastic serological pipette, 10-mL	Sarstedt	86.1254.001
Plastic serological pipette, 5mL	Sarstedt	86.1253.001
Plastic serological pipette, 1mL	Fisher	13-678-11B
Glass serological pipette, borosilicate disposable	Fisherbrand	13-678-27E
Polypropylene microcentrifuge tube	Fisher	02-681-273

2.2 Culture reagents

Item	Supplier	Catalogue #	Stock conc.	Working conc.	Storage temp.
DMEM/F12 with GlutaMAX-I	Life Technologies	10565018	1X	1X	Stock: 4°C Working: 4°C
Antibiotic- Antimycotic	Gibco	15240062	100X	1X	Stock: -20°C Working: 4°C
Laminin	Sigma	L2020	1mg/mL	5µg/mL	Stock: -80°C Working: 4°C
	Invitrogen	23017-015			
Accutase	Life Technologies	A11105-01	1X	1X	Stock: -20°C Working: 4°C

Item	Supplier	Catalogue #	Stock conc.	Working conc.	Storage temp.
Y27632 (ROCK inhibitor)	Selleckchem	S1049	10mM	10µM	Stock: -80°C Working: 4°C
MEM Non-Essential Amino Acids	Wisent	321-011-EL	100X	1X	Stock: 4°C
2-Mercaptoethanol	Life Technologies	21985023	55mM	55µM	4°C
N2 Supplement	Gibco	17502-048	100X	1X	-20°C
B27 Supplement without vitamin A	Life Technologies	12587-010	50X	1X	-20°C
All-trans Retinoic Acid	Sigma-Aldrich	R2625	1mM	100nM	Stock: - 80°C Working: 4°C
SB431542	Selleckchem	S1067	10mM	10µM	Stock: - 80°C Working: 4°C
DMH1	Selleckchem	S7146	4mM	2µM	Stock: -80°C Working: 4°C
Puromorphamine	Sigma-Aldrich	SML-0868	2mM	2µM	Stock: - 80°C Working: 4°C
Recombinant human PDGF-AA	Peprtech	100-13A	10µg/mL	10ng/mL	Stock: - 80°C Working: 4°C
Recombinant human IGF-I, CF	Peprtech	100-11	10µg/mL	10ng/mL	Stock: - 80°C Working: 4°C
Recombinant human HGF	R&D Systems	294-HG-025	10µg/mL	5ng/mL	Stock: - 80°C Working: 4°C
Neurotrophin-3 (NT3)	Peprtech	450-03	10µg/mL	10ng/mL	Stock: - 80°C Working: 4°C
Insulin solution, human	Sigma-Aldrich	I2643	10mg/mL	25µg/mL	4°C
Biotin	Sigma-Aldrich	B4639	100µg/mL	100ng/mL	Stock: - 80°C Working: 4°C
Dibutyl cAMP (db cAMP)	Carbosynth	ND07996	10mM	1µM	Stock: - 80°C Working: 4°C
3,3,5-Triiodo-L-thyronine (T3)	Sigma-Aldrich	T6397	60µg/mL	60ng/mL	Stock: - 80°C Working: 4°C
L-Ascorbic acid (AA)	Sigma-Aldrich	A5960	200mM	200µM	Stock: - 80°C Working: 4°C
Recombinant human FGF-2 basic	Peprtech	100-18B	10µg/mL	20ng/mL	Stock: - 80°C Working: 4°C
Heparin	Sigma-Aldrich	H3149	2mg/mL	2µg/mL	Stock: -80°C Working: 4°C
Poly-L-ornithine	Sigma-Aldrich	P3655	1mg/mL	10µg/mL	Stock: -20°C Working: 4°C
mTeSR1	StemCell	05851	1X	1X	Stock: -20°C
mTesR Supplement		05852	5X	1X	Working: 4°C

Item	Supplier	Catalogue #	Stock conc.	Working conc.	Storage temp.
Matrigel Matrix hESC-qualified	Corning	354277	100X	1X	Stock: -80°C Working: thaw at 4°C
Gentle dissociation reagent	Stem Cell	7174	1X	1X	RT

2.3 Equipment

Item	Supplier	Catalogue #
Cell culture incubator	ThermoScientific	SteriCycle Model 370 Ref#20
Cell culture water bath	Fisher Scientific	IsoTemp GPD20
Centrifuge	Eppendorf 5702	022626001
Light microscope	Motic	AE2000
Cell counter	Logos Biosystems	LUNA-II Automated cell counter
Cell counting slide	Logos Biosystems	05181401

3 Protocol

3.1 Coating of culture vessels

Materials:

- Culture vessels (flasks or plates; if using coverslips, add to plate wells)
- PO (1mg/mL)
- Laminin (1mg/mL)
- 1x PBS
- DMEM/F12
- Antibiotic-Antimycotic
- 37°C/5% CO₂ cell culture incubator

Procedure:

1. Prepare PO working solution by adding 500 µL of PO stock solution to 50mL 1x PBS.
 - Thaw PO stock solution at 4°C.
 - Ensure transfer of all PO stock solution by rinsing tube with PBS twice.
 - The PO working solution can be stored at 4°C for up to 2 months.

Table 2. Recommended volumes for PO coating

Plate type	Volume of PO solution
T-25cm ² flask	3ml/flask
T-75cm ² flask	7ml/flask
6-well plate	1ml/well
12-well plate	1ml/well
24-well plate	0.5ml/well
60mm dish	2ml/well
100mm dish	7ml/dish

2. Apply recommended volume of PO solution to culture vessel and swirl to spread across surfaces.
 - **IMPORTANT:** Ensure culture surfaces are coated completely and evenly. Do not let surfaces dry. Uneven coating or evaporation of coating may affect cell distribution.
3. Incubate culture vessel for at least 2 hours or overnight at 37°C.
4. Aspirate PO solution from culture vessel and wash surfaces three times with 1x PBS.

5. Prepare laminin working solution by adding 100µl of laminin stock solution and 200 µl of Antibiotic Antimycotic to 20 mL of cold DMEM/F12.
 - **IMPORTANT:** Store laminin stock solution at -80°C and thaw at 4°C before using. At room temperature laminin easily adsorbs to plastic and tends to form aggregates.
 - The laminin working solution can be stored at 4°C for up to 2 weeks.

Table 3. Recommended volumes for laminin coating

Plate type	Volume of laminin solution
T-25cm ² flask	2,5ml/flask
T-75cm ² flask	7ml/flask
6-well plate	1ml/well
12-well plate	500µl /well
24-well plate	300µl/well
60mm dish	2ml/well
100mm dish	7ml/dish

6. Apply recommended volume of laminin solution to culture vessel and swirl to spread across surfaces.
 - **IMPORTANT:** Ensure culture surfaces are coated completely and evenly. Do not let surfaces dry. Uneven coating or evaporation of coating may affect cell distribution.
7. Incubate culture vessel at 37°C for 2 hours.
8. If plating cells on culture vessel immediately, aspirate laminin solution and proceed with plating. If not plating cells on culture vessel immediately, do not aspirate laminin solution and store culture vessel in a 37°C incubator for up to 3 days.
 - **IMPORTANT:** If using PO/laminin-coated culture vessels that have been stored (i.e. if not using immediately after coating procedure), check quality of coating before plating cells: uneven coating, presence of clumps or evaporation of coating may affect cell distribution.

3.2 Preparation of culture media

All the components of the media used during the entire protocol will be added to the same **Basal medium**:

Component	Initial concentration	Final concentration	Dilution
NEAA			100X
N2			100X
B27 without vitamin A*			50X
Anti-Anti			100X
2-mercaptoethanol	55mM	55uM	1000X
Insulin	10mg/mL	25ug/mL	400X
Heparin	2mg/mL	2ug/mL	1000X
DMEM/F12 + GlutaMAX-I			

*It is very important for the differentiation of oligodendrocytes to avoid using vitamin A. The use of normal vitamin A-supplemented B27 may result in the arrest of cells in the OPC phase.

Neural induction/patterning medium

Component	Initial concentration	Final concentration	Dilution
SB431542	10mM	10uM	1000X
DMH1	4mM	2uM	2000X
Retinoic Acid	1mM	0.1uM	10.000X
Basal Medium			

Ventralization medium

Component	Initial concentration	Final concentration	Dilution
Retinoic Acid	1mM	0.1uM	10.000X
Puromorphamine	2mM	1uM	2000X
Basal Medium			

*from day 12 add 20ng/mL of bFGF

PDGF medium

Component	Initial concentration	Final concentration	Dilution
PDGF-AA	10ug/mL	10ng/mL	1000X
IGF-1	10ug/mL	10ng/mL	1000X
NT-3	10ug/mL	10ng/mL	1000X
HGF	10ug/mL	5ng/mL	2000X
T3	60ug/mL	60ng/mL	1000X
Biotin	100ug/mL	100ng/mL	1000X
cAMP	1mM	1uM	1000X
Basal medium			

Differentiation medium (or AA medium)

Component	Initial concentration	Final concentration	Dilution
AA	200mM	200uM	1000X
T3	60ug/mL	60ng/mL	1000X
Biotin	100ug/mL	100ng/mL	1000X
cAMP	1mM	1uM	1000X
Basal Medium			

3.3 Preparation of iPSC cultures for Oligodendrocyte Differentiation

Materials:

- Plate of 70-90% confluent iPSCs
- Matrigel-coated 6-well plate
- Gentle dissociation reagent
- 15-mL conical tubes
- mTeSR1 with supplements or Essential 8
- Y-27632 (ROCK inhibitor)
- 37°C/5% CO₂ cell culture incubator

Procedure:

1. Aspirate media from cells and rinse with 5 mL of DMEM/F12 containing 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic. Add 5 mL Gentle Cell Dissociation Reagent and incubate at room temperature for 4 to 6 minutes or at 37°C for 3 to 5 minutes. Refer also to SOP [EDDU 002 02](#).
 - Ensure that regions of differentiation have been removed by aspiration prior to passaging.
2. Aspirate the Gentle Cell Dissociation Reagent and wash cells with 5 mL of DMEM/F12 containing 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic. Add 5 mL of DMEM/F12 containing 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic to cells and gently detach the colonies with a cell scraper.
3. Transfer the detached cell aggregates to a 15-mL conical tube. Rinse the dish with an additional 5 mL of DMEM/F12 containing 1x Antibiotic-Antimycotic to collect any remaining cell aggregates and transfer to the tube. Pellet cell aggregates by centrifuging at 1200 rpm (200 g) for 3 minutes.
 - Take care to avoid breaking up cell aggregates.
4. Gently aspirate supernatant. Carefully pipette the cell aggregate mixture up and down 3 to 5 times with a glass pipet in complete media to break up the cell aggregates.
 - Do not create a single-cell suspension.
5. Plate 8×10^4 to 1×10^5 cells per well on a Matrigel-coated six-well plate that already contains 1.5 ml of mTeSR1 (or Essential 8) supplemented with 10 μ M Y27632 per well.
 - This density of plated iPSCs is optimized to give a confluent well by day 8 and multilayered structures by day 12 of differentiation.
6. Incubate the cells for 24 h at 37 °C, 5% CO₂.
7. The next day, remove the old medium and add 2 ml of fresh mTeSR1 (or Essential 8) in each well.
8. Incubate the cells for 1–2 days, until iPSC colonies reach a diameter of 100–250 μ m.

3.4 Differentiation of OLIG2+ neural progenitors (sc-NPCs)

Materials:

- iPSCs cultured in 6-well plate
- 37°C/5% CO₂ cell culture incubator
- Accutase
- Neural induction/patterning medium
- Ventralization medium
- bFGF 10µg/mL

Procedure:

1. Once colonies are ~100–250 µm in diameter (see **Figure 2**), aspirate the old medium and induce differentiation by adding 2 ml of neural induction/patterning medium to each well. This is day 0.
 - Adding RA at a low concentration (100nM) from day 0 of the differentiation greatly improves the yield of OLIG2+ progenitors at day 12.
2. Incubate the plate at 37 °C, 5% CO₂, and perform media changes every day for 8 days, adding fresh RA, SB431542 and LDN193189 to the medium every day.
3. On day 8, switch to ventralization medium and incubate for 4 days, changing the medium daily, adding fresh RA and Purmorphamine to the medium every day.
 - The medium will become yellowish owing to the rapid expansion of the cells and their increasing numbers. This is why it is important to change the media every day on the cells to provide the required nutrients.
 - By day 8, cells should be confluent and PAX6 expression should be at its peak.
 - By day 12, overconfluent cells piling up and 3D structures should be clearly visible. This is an important checkpoint before proceeding with the differentiation (see **Figure 2**).
 - **PAUSE POINT:** At this point cells can be frozen. Otherwise proceed with the aggregation and expansion of OLIG2+ cells.
4. Aspirate the medium and add 1 ml of prewarmed Accutase.
5. Incubate at 37 °C for 5 min (or until cells completely detach from the plate)
6. Dilute the Accutase solution by adding 2 ml of DMEM/F12 medium.
7. With a p1000 pipette, pipette the mixture 2–5 times to dissociate the culture into a single-cell suspension.
 - In order to obtain a better single-cell suspension a double-tip can be used by attaching a p200 pipette tip in front of a p1000tip.

8. Transfer the cells to a 15-ml conical tube and dilute the solution further by adding another 5 ml of DMEM/F12.
9. Collect the cells by centrifugation at 1200rpm (200g) for 4 min at RT.
10. Resuspend the cell pellet in 1 ml of ventralization medium supplemented with 20ng/mL bFGF and distribute the single-cell suspension into a 100mm Petri dish containing 9mL of supplemented ventralization medium.
 - The addition of bFGF maximizes the efficiency of sphere formation and promotes the differentiation of proliferating OPCs.
11. Incubate the plate for 2 days at 37 °C, 5% CO₂.
12. Transfer the medium containing the cell aggregates into a 15-ml conical tube and centrifuge for 2 min at 100g at RT.
13. Remove three-quarters of the medium and add 6.5ml of fresh supplemented ventralization medium.
14. Return the aggregates to the same Petri dish and swirl the plate to redistribute the aggregates.
15. Repeat medium change steps every other day until day 20 of differentiation.
 - According to the rate of expansion and the change in coloration of media, this can be performed twice a week.
 - **PAUSE POINT:** At this point cells can be frozen as explained in the next section. Otherwise proceed with section 3.6 Differentiation of OPC and Oligodendrocytes in adherent cultures.

Figure 2. Brightfield image of cell morphology during the differentiation protocol

3.5 Freezing of OLIG2+ spheres

Materials:

- Spheres culture at day 20 in a 100mm Petri dish
- Cryovials
- 15-mL conical tube
- 5-mL glass pipet
- Accutase
- DMEM/F12
- Antibiotic-antimycotic
- 20% DMSO in FBS
- Centrifuge
- 37°C/5% CO₂ cell culture incubator

Procedure:

1. Collect the spheres in a 15-mL conical tube.
2. Wash the plate with 3-mL DMEM/F12 with Antibiotic-antimycotic.
3. Centrifuge the suspension at 1200rpm (200g) for 4 min.
4. Aspirate the medium and add 0.5-1 mL of prewarmed Accutase.
5. Incubate at 37 °C for 5 min (or until cells completely detach from the plate)
6. Dilute the Accutase solution by adding 2 ml of DMEM/F12 medium.
7. With a p1000 pipette, pipette the mixture 2–5 times to dissociate the culture into a single-cell suspension.
 - In order to obtain a better single-cell suspension a double-tip can be used by attaching a p200 pipette tip in front of a p1000tip.
8. Incubate at 37°C for 5-10 min.
9. Gently aspirate the supernatant. Gently resuspend the cell pellet in FBS in half the volume needed to form 1 mL of cell aggregate mixture per cryovial.
 - In this case, each Petri dish will have enough spheres to freeze 3 cryovials so 1.5 mL should be added. This amount should be adjusted according to the amount of spheres generated.
10. Add an equal volume of 20% DMSO/FBS to the cell aggregate mixture to obtain a final DMSO concentration of 10%. Mix well.
11. Transfer 1 mL of cell aggregate mixture to each cryovial.
12. Place cryovials in a cryo-box and store at –20°C for 3 to 4 hours. Transfer cryo-box to –80°C and store overnight. Transfer cryovials to liquid nitrogen.
 - Do not store cryovials at –80°C for more than 3 days. OPCs are sensitive to changes in temperature. Long-term storage at –80°C reduces cell survival after thawing.

3.6 Differentiation and expansion of OPC and differentiation into myelinating Oligodendrocytes

Materials:

- Day 20 spheres or frozen cryovials of day 20 progenitors
- 37°C/5% CO₂ cell culture incubator
- 15-mL conical tube
- 5-mL glass pipette
- PO/laminin-coated vessels
- PDGF medium
- AA medium

Procedure:

1. On day 20, with a glass pipette, transfer the aggregates to a 15-ml conical tube and wait for 3 min for the aggregates to sink to the bottom of the tube.
 - If the culture is started from frozen vials, plate the content of one vial in 10-mL of PDGF medium in a 100mm Petri dish. Proceed with **step 5**.
 - **OPTIONAL:** 20ng/mL of bFGF can be added to the thawed culture to speed up sphere formation.
2. Remove two-thirds of the medium and replenish it with PDGF medium.
3. Gently pipette five times up and down with a p1000 pipette.
 - It is important to break apart the aggregates that stick to each other through gentle pipetting.
4. Return the aggregates to the same Petri dish.
5. Repeat medium change every other day until day 30 of differentiation.
6. On day 30, transfer the aggregates in a PO/laminin-coated vessel containing PDGF medium.
 - Plating two spheres per cm² ensures that cells will migrate out of the spheres and fill the whole well around day 60 without the need for passaging the cells.
 - For large production of OPCs an entire Petri dish of spheres can be plated in a T75 flask.
7. Incubate the plate at 37 °C, 5% CO₂.
8. Every other day carefully replenish two-thirds of the medium with fresh PDGF medium until day 75 of differentiation. After day 55 most of the cells should show a bipolar or tri-polar morphology typical of OPCs (see **Figure 3**).

- **IMPORTANT:** Avoid sudden movements when you transfer the plate from the incubator, especially after day 40, as the cells can potentially detach from the plate, typically in the form of a sheet.
 - After day 55, OPCs can be passaged in new PO/laminin-coated vessels in the presence of the ROCK inhibitor (Y27632).
 - **PAUSE POINT:** Cells can be frozen at day 75.
9. At day 75 carefully replenish two-thirds of the medium with fresh AA medium.
 10. Repeat **step 9** every 2-3 days (or once a week) until day 95. Oligodendrocytes should have a typical multi-branched shape and should be positive to the nuclear marker SOX10 and the surface antigen O4 (see **Figure 4**).

Figure 3. Morphology of OPCs at day 55 of differentiation

Figure 4. SOX10/O4-positive Oligodendrocytes at the end of the protocol